

ETERNAL TRACE IN HISTORY

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Annotation: This article tells about the diligence and efforts of Professor, Doctor of Historical Sciences Ubaydulla Uvatov in studying the life and work of leading scholars from Central Asia, in particular from Movarounnahr .

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается об усердии и усилиях профессора Убайдуллы Уватова, доктора исторических наук, в изучении жизни и деятельности ведущих ученых Средней Азии, в частности из Мовароуннахра.

The key words : Ubaydulla Uvatov , Karshi , Silk Road, oriental studies , source studies, the arabic language, history, Central Asia scholars

As we know, Uzbekistan is one of the countries on the Silk Road. Examples show that Central Asia has left an indelible mark on the development of Muslim culture. Born and raised in the land of ancient Movarounnahr Imam Bukhari, Imam Termezi, Imam Moturudi, Muhammad Khorezmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Ahmad Fergani, who became famous in the Islamic world for their scientific courage and great discoveries. The lives and activities of our dear scholars, great thinkers such as Mahmud Zamakhshari, Burhoniddin Margaroni, Khoja Ahror Vali, Mirzo Ulugbek and Alisher Navoi are closely connected with Islamic culture and civilization. Located at an important crossroads of different civilizations and cultures, our country is known as a country that has made an invaluable contribution to human development, as well as one of the richest sources of manuscripts that form the core of the cultural heritage of Oriental scholars.¹ The Institute of Oriental Studies named after Beruni holds a significant part of this wealth in the manuscript treasury. Translating them into Uzbek, publishing them in conversion

¹ O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi "Ilm-u ma'rifatga bag'shida umr. Ubaydulla Uvatov – tarix fanlari dokrtori, professor"//O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi nashriyot-matbaa birlashmasi Toshkent-2020.-174 b.;

and facsimile has already become one of the priorities of today. Ubaydulla Karimov, Burivoy Ahmedov, Ismatulla Abdullayev, Sodiq Mirzayev, Yunusjon Hakimjanov, Asomiddin Urinboyev, Mahmud Hasani, Naim Norkulov, Dilorom Yusupova, Ashraf Ahmedov, Ismail Bekjanov, Omonulla Buriyev, Gulom Karimov and along with another scholars, there is no doubt that the work of teacher Ubaydulla Uvatov also serves as a translation, a model in their research, a great school of experience for today's young professionals. Towards the end of his life, the scientist wrote reviews of research at the Institute of Oriental Studies, and with his valuable insights, he never tired of supporting young people in the path of science, never giving them the right direction.

On June 16, 2002, Ubaydulla Uvatov, an orientalist and Islamic scholar, defended his doctoral dissertation on "The role of scholars of Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the development of hadith (Al-Bukhari, Muslim, At-Termizi)." and conveyed to the younger generation his rich and invaluable heritage, which embodied his ideas and has not lost its scientific and human value even today, and thus became known among our nation. Ubaydulla Uvatov has published 15 books and more than 60 articles. The rich scientific heritage created by the scientist, his works are serving as a role model for young people. Ubaydulla Uvatov's speeches at scientific conferences, a number of scientific books and articles and scientific debates, his independent expression of ideas, his writing and speaking in both Uzbek, Arabic and Russian are appreciated by people. Ubaydulla Uvatov has established a unique school of Oriental Studies in Uzbekistan and is a scholar who has made a significant contribution to the development of the sciences of hadith, Islamic history and source studies in our country.² The basis of his research is to provide information about the way of life, invaluable works and classics of thinkers who lived in our country, to highlight their contribution to the development of science.

Professor Ubaydulla Uvatov, a world-renowned doctor of historical sciences, has made an invaluable contribution to the study of the legacy of scholars who grew up in our country and contributed to the development of various sciences. Today, the scientist is considered a mentor by all the smaller orientalists and scholars in our country.

² O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi "Ilm-u ma'rifatga bag' shida umr. Ubaydulla Uvatov – tarix fanlari dokrtori, professor"//O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi nashriyot-matbaa birlashmasi Toshkent-2020.-174 b.;

Although most of them did not conduct face-to-face research with Ubaydulla Uvatov, they also read their writings and articles and used them in their research. They consider with respect this scholar as a teacher.

The fruitful work of the scientist, his zeal in studying the lives of great scholars who grew up in Central Asia, especially in Movarounnahr, who made a significant contribution to world civilization, his research in introducing great scholars to the people were appreciated. He was awarded the honorary title of “Ozbeksiton Respublikasida xizmat ko’rsatgan yoshlar murabbiysi”, the order of “Mehnat shuhrati” and in 2020 the order of “Fidokorona xizmatlari uchun”.³ Throughout his life, he never tired of studying the scientific and enlightenment heritage of our great ancestors, he always considered it an honor for him to work, he worked tirelessly in summer and winter. His research has left an indelible mark on the pages of history.

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³ <https://n.ziyouz.com/books/islomiy/tarix/Ubaydulla%20Uvatov.%20Muslim%20ibn%20al-Hajjoj.pdf>